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THE GEOTHERMAL CAPACITY-BUILDING INITIATIVES BY THE MINISTRY OF ENERGY AND MINERAL RESOURCES

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ABSTRACT

Indonesia targets 23% of renewable energy in the energy mix in 2025. This target includes around 5% energy generated from geothermal or around 7200MW installed capacity. The Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (MEMR), oversees this target by issuing regulations as a stimulus to support the achievement of the 2025's goal. The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources also conducts various capacity building programs for geothermal human resources through the Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation (Dirjen EBTKE) and Human Resource Development Agency of MEMR (BPSDM ESDM). This paper discusses the role of these two institutions in geothermal development, focusing on capacity building in recent years and proposes some improvement strategies. This paper will also present several cooperation programs from abroad to develop geothermal human resources in Indonesia. This paper will give special attention to geothermal drilling training and certification programs as an evaluation and input for continuous improvement.

INTRODUCTION

The government of Indonesia (GoI) targets the portions of new and renewable energy in the national energy mix to reach 23 percent In 2025. This target is also written in National Energy Policy (KEN) and the General Plan for National Energy (RUEN). This goal is also the GoI's commitment to the Paris Agreement in 2015.

However, until the end of 2018, the total installed capacity of the Renewable Energy Generation is 12.39% with a geothermal generating capacity of 1,948.5 MW (MEMR, 2019). It is estimated that for seven years, geothermal power can add about 2% of the use of renewable energy in a national energy mix followed by a hydroelectric power plant and solar power plant.

A significant increase in human resources is needed to achieve the 2025's geothermal goal. EHE (2015) estimated that to meet the MEMR development plans, Indonesia requires 1,300 to 2,200 additional

geothermal trained engineers and scientists by 2020, and a further 500 to 800 by 2025. There is also a need for around 260 central and regional government regulatory staff to be trained in appropriate areas of geothermal expertise, and further staffing resources in training institutions.

The MEMR is a ministry that has the duty and responsibility to regulate and supervise the geothermal industry so that it develops well. Furthermore, the development of geothermal human resources in addition to the task of the ministry of education through formal education is also supported by MEMR through Dirjen EBTKE and BPSDM.

SKILL REQUIREMENTS AT GEOTHERMAL DEVELOPMENT STAGES

Development of a geothermal project according to Gehringer & Loksha (2012) and Hervey et al. (2014) is divided into eight phases, namely preliminary survey, exploration, test drilling, project review and planning, field development, power plant construction, commissioning, and operation and monitoring. Each of these stages requires skilled and competent personnel to perform specific tasks. Campen, O'Sullivan, & Rai-IRENA (2015) identify the typical types of expertise needed for each step of the geothermal project as follows:

- Preliminary survey and exploration phases require geologists, geochemists, geophysicists, hydrologists, and engineers;
- Test drilling phase requires drilling engineers, crew and managers, geologists, reservoir engineers and modelers, heavy transport personnel, and construction personnel;
- Project review and planning, field development, power plant construction, and commissioning phases require drilling engineers, crew and managers, plant and prospect engineers and managers, reservoir engineers and modelers, heavy transport personnel, and construction personnel;
- Operation and monitoring phases require steam field and plant managers and engineers, operators and technicians, reservoir engineers and modelers, geologists, geochemists,

geophysicists, and service and maintenance personnel.

In addition to the above roles, every stage of geothermal development also requires enabling personnel such as environmental, regulatory, and investment experts as well as general personnel covering social experts, lawyers, financial analysts, contracting personnel, coordinators, and project managers.

Preliminary survey

At this stage, the geologist is obligated to identify the geological setting, geothermal potential type, and assess the possible geothermal evidence to guide further activities. Surveillance data of existing geothermal areas is also needed to be collected by air imaging or remote sensing of satellites.

Moreover, hydrologists are tasked with identifying water resources and hot springs, while general personnel is required to analyze information from available literature such as any drilling data, petroleum or mineral exploration history, and informal data from residents as a useful background to understanding subsurface conditions.

Exploration

Once the results of the initial survey show satisfactory results and meet the legal requirements, the next stage of surface exploration can commence. Generally, the geoscientists (geologists, geochemists, and geophysicists) should be able to collect geoscientific data with practical surveying of the surface and sub-surface to minimize uncertainty. This activity is mainly related to the approximate main reservoir parameters such as temperature, depth, area, mineralized zone, and permeability to prove resources. They should also provide primary environmental data and assist monitoring throughout the life of the project by integrating all geoscience aspects related to geothermal systems to create conceptual models that guide exploration, drilling and further management of resources.

Test drilling

This stage is a significant step to confirm the existence, precise location, and reservoir potential by involving more engineers than scientists. Predictions about the productivity of the well are rarely accurate before drilling commences. Gehringer & Loksha (2012) and Hervey et al. (2014) estimate that about 10 to 30 percent of drilled production wells are producing remarkably low power or are very weak to harness. Although test drilling usually drills slim holes, the skill required in this stage is identical to drilling for production and drilling of reinjection wells. Figure 1 describes the companies and experts involved in the drilling operation of an oil well. Nonetheless, until recently this scheme is still being applied in geothermal drilling.

Ford (2004) describes the roles and functions of those who manage drilling operations as follows:

- The operating company or operator is the main company that manages drilling and production operations. Operators are tasked to prepare designs, work programs, transportation services, consumable goods, and support for drilling operations. Operators typically employ drilling contractors and service companies to drill a well.
- Drilling contractors are tasked to provide drilling rigs and personnel to drill wells, so they are also responsible for maintaining drill rigs and training personnel required to operate the rigs.
- The service company provides specific specialized skills or equipment such as logging and surveying during drilling so that it is also tasked to develop and maintain the equipment and hire staff as operators.

Furthermore, some of the key personnel involved in a drilling operation are as follows:

1. The company man is a representative of the operators who is placed on the rig to ensure drilling operations run as planned (schedule and budget), make decisions affecting well progress, and manage the availability of drilling equipment and materials (Ford, 2004).
2. The drilling engineer is responsible for designing wells and casing along with the cementing program, drilling rig selection and other drilling support equipment.
3. Geologists are responsible for assisting and supervising drilling, geological logging, analyzing and interpreting drill cuttings and cores, helping to determine the productivity of wells, determining drilling and different depth, and estimating corrosion risk.
4. The rig manager is the highest representative of the rig contracting company whose job it is to ensure the rigs are provided according to the operator's requirements (as per the contract).
5. The tool pusher is responsible for overseeing the daily activities of all rig crews on the rig site, including equipment maintenance.
6. The driller is tasked to prepare drill series such as Bottom Hole Assembly (BHA) and BOP and communicate directly with crews.
7. Drilling crews are working under the direction of the driller and are tasked with performing manual activities related to well drilling which generally comprise of:
 - a) Derrickman oversees helping driller running in hole or pull out BHA of the hole (trimming).
 - b) Floorman or roughneck unplug the drill pipe circuit, install the sheath, install rig tong, operate spinner, and so forth.
 - c) Supporting crews such as mechanics, electricians, tow carriers, roustabouts, and others.
8. The mud engineer is tasked to prepare drilling mud by the drilling program that has been approved.

9. The directional driller is the person responsible for directional drilling by the direction/target set in the drilling program.
10. Heavy transport and construction personnel are assigned for the transportation and construction of drilling rigs.
11. Reservoir engineers and modelers at this stage will update the models that have been made at the exploration stage using data from the geoscientist obtained from drilling.

Figure 1. Personnel involved in drilling an oil well (adapted from Ford, 2004)

Project review and planning

This stage usually only involves general staff for data evaluation from the previous stage of the preliminary survey, exploration, and test drilling. They will then conduct a feasibility study covering the financial aspect, risk analysis, construction, and drilling program to determine the amount of investment required for the most effective program. The reservoir modelers will process the data into a numerical reservoir model to estimate the possibility of production per production well.

Field development

This stage begins with the drilling of production wells and injection wells by drilling engineers and crew. This activity involves expertise as described in the test-drilling phase. At this stage, construction personnel builds pipelines to connect wells to a gathering system and a power plant. On the other hand, the reservoir engineer will calculate the exact production wells to produce optimal production. They should also select the location of the reinjection wells to restore the geothermal fluid to the reservoir and support the pressure on the reservoir but should prevent the cooling of the geothermal reservoir. Furthermore, the hydrologist will assist the reservoir engineer in mapping the underground flow pattern from the numerical reservoir analysis based on the conceptual and mathematical model of the reservoir made by the modeler of the reservoir.

Power plant construction

At this stage, plant engineers will plan and design the power plant according to the specifications of successful drilling results. The construction personnel is responsible for installing a steam collection system with one or more separators, turbines, generators, condensers and cooling

systems either utilizing water or air. Pipe installation is also carried out for reinjection of the cooled geothermal fluid to the reservoir through reinjection wells. Moreover, civil works and infrastructure such as roads and well pad access are also built at this stage as well as the construction of transmission lines through substations.

Commissioning

This phase mainly involves general personnel, including lawyers, financial analysts, contracting staff, and project managers to solve many technical problems such as contracts with procurement, engineering, and construction contractors of power plants. Furthermore, the power plant engineer is tasked with adjusting the efficiency of the power plant and ensuring its operability satisfies its particular design conditions by testing all the components and related equipment (Gehring and Loksha, 2012).

Operation and maintenance

Here is an outline of the duties of each staff member at this stage:

1. Operators or technicians are tasked with conducting steam operations in steam fields to ensure that a steam supply to the generator remains optimal and operates equipment at power plant installations.
2. Steam field engineers are tasked with designing and executing new production well drilling to increase or maintain production capacity, and drilling of new reinjection wells if necessary.
3. Service and maintenance personnel are tasked with performing routine maintenance to ensure optimum and safe factory performance, and prompt repairs to solve problems such as scaling, and casing failure due to corrosion or collapse.
4. Plant managers and engineers are tasked with improving plant efficiency and solving production or injection problems such as changes in injection strategies from studying reservoir modeling that is continuously updated by reservoir engineers and modelers according to operating conditions, geophysical observations and chemical analysis.
5. Supervisors of production operations are tasked with planning, controlling, supervising, evaluating, and handling the work when there is a problem in the care of the well.
6. Production operators are tasked with preparing activity units and conducting well maintenance, including killing a well.
7. The geoscientist is responsible for monitoring surface activity, potential contaminants (water and gas), down-hole surveys, production well testing and injection wells, geochemical analysis, and geophysical analysis including microseismic to determine the direction of fluid flow. The results of the data are used to establish

the baseline data for subsequent monitoring of the geothermal system.

Geothermal development requires many staff and experts at every stage. Therefore, human resource development (HRD) is also an essential aspect in the successful development of geothermal drilling. This study will focus more on the drilling competencies since these are the most expensive and crucial stages of the development. The drilling engineers and crew are also the most prospective target for skill transfers from the oil and gas industries to geothermal business, due to the frequent exchange and sharing of technologies between them.

REGULATION ON GEOTHERMAL HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

President decree No 22 the Year 2017

Indonesia national energy policy is described in the Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 22 the Year 2017 About the General Plan of National Energy (RUEN). The National Energy Board (DEN) as the drafter of RUEN performs a series of modeling as a reference in energy development in Indonesia until 2050. The result of the modeling of primary energy supply shows that geothermal contribution to new Renewable Energy (EBT) supply is 21.8 MTOE or 23.6% in 2025 and 58.8 MTOE or 18.6% by 2050. While the modeling results of the development of EBT power plants show geothermal generating 7,241.5 MW in 2025 and 17,546 MW in 2050 or 59% of the geothermal potential of 29.5 GW.

However, this RUEN does not specify as much about the development of human resources as a step to achieve the target of geothermal power plant development (PLTP). Strategic actions for the development of PLTP according to RUEN include improving the quality and quantity of potential resources and geothermal resource surveys, preliminary survey and exploration assignments by government agencies or business entities and assignments of State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN) or Public Service Bodies (BLU) to develop PLTP.

2015-2019 MEMR strategic plan

Based on the 2015-2019 MEMR strategic plan stipulated through the Minister of Energy and Mineral Resources Decree No. 13 of 2015, the strategic targets and indicators of MEMR performance in 2015-2019 in terms of EBT development is to increase the installed capacity of EBT power plants to 16,996 MW by 2019 with the target installed capacity of Geothermal Energy being 3195 MW.

On the other hand, the quality of human resources targets include:

1. Organizing competency-based education and training with the aim of 65% of the total training conducted in 2019.

2. Increased certification of Energy and Mineral Resource personnel
3. Competency enhancement and teaching staff certification
4. Acceleration of the process to implement professional training institutions accreditation by the MEMR Education and Training Agency
5. Increased cooperation with Local government agencies, the private sector, KKS and Stakeholders
6. Optimizing and improving the quality of education and training facilities
7. Acceleration of the Indonesian national competency work standard (SKKNI) in the Energy and Mineral Resource sector
8. Accelerating the preparation of the Polytechnic of Akamigas infrastructure.
9. Organizing activities to improve community competency to fill the opportunities for skilled labor markets at home and abroad by utilizing CSR funds to encourage the acceleration of the supply of prevocational energy in the Energy and Mineral Resource sector

CAPACITY BUILDING PROGRAM BY THE MEMR

Directorate General of New, Renewable Energy, and Energy Conservation

The Geothermal Directorate has designed a master plan for developing human resources in the geothermal sector which can be divided into 3 (three) stages, namely increasing geothermal awareness among campuses, linking & matching steps between research and industry, and building human resource competence.

The stage of increasing geothermal awareness among campuses is an introduction of geothermal activities to colleges. This activity has been started since 2012 through Program Geothermal Going to Campus (GGtC). These activities have been carried out on several universities with the subjects including the linking & matching stage is an effort to bridge industrial and school needs through the application of SKKNI in the world of education and optimization of research and development through cooperation between universities, government, and industry.

Seventeen universities already have involved in the program namely ITS, USU, Trisakti University, UNILA, UNDIP, UNSRI, UNAND, University of Mataram, Institute Technology of Medan, UNSRAT, UPN, UNSYAH, UNSOED, University of Jambi, Nusa Cendana University, UNPAD, and UNHAS.

In the universities have been conducting two activities, the general studium and project case study. The general studium, so-called "Kelas Umum", is to give general understanding about geothermal in several subjects to the lecturers and

students. Whereas, the project case, so-called Kelas Khusus is a days simulation as practitioners, how to evaluate one of the stages to develop geothermal potential. The simulation was starting from subsurface analysis up to project financial analysis. Until 2010, the activities were a building of human resource competence stage. One of the activities is the implementation phase of the SKKNI. The application of research and development is divided into two focuses, namely the development of the core competency focus of the geothermal sector and the focus of competency in supporting the geothermal industry.

As parts of the GGtC program, Directorate of Geothermal, funded by the World Bank grant, will hold a certification for the geothermal geologist in expert level. The certification will involve five universities within the program. Up to now, there are 3 (three) SKKNI. The SKKNI's are for the geothermal geologist, geothermal geochemist and geothermal geophysicist.

Besides SKKNI, in geothermal, there are three Special Competence Standard (Standard Kompetensi Khusus), namely Pengawas Operasional Pertama (POP), Pengawas Operasional Madya (POM), and Pengawas Operasional Utama (POU). There are 1548 experts in total have been certified, 1230 in POP level, 233 in POM level, and 85 in POU level.

Human Resource Development Agency

Supervisor training at PPSDM KEBTKE

The Center for Human Resource Development of Electricity, New, Renewable, and Energy Conservation (PPSDM KEBTKE) is the only training center under the ministry responsible for geothermal fields as part of renewable energy sources. However, due to the vast area of responsibility for this center, training is more devoted to downstream industries or electricity generation. Even though the center provides training for industries and government, geothermal-related training that is conducted mainly for government officials includes technical training for geothermal working area, technical training introduction of a geothermal working budget and expenditure plan, and specialized training of HSE geothermal inspection.

In 2018, the center had organized three geothermal power plant supervision training (POP and POM) and planned to hold a similar training program again this year.

PPSDM KEBTKE has also hosted a New Zealand Support for Training in the Indonesia Geothermal Sector (NZSTIGS) program that has signed on September 5, 2018 by GoI and New Zealand to develop and provide practical training for geothermal technicians and operators for the next five years. The program is called Trains the Trainers

(TTT) Mastery Level which was held from October 15, 2018, for four weeks with instructors from the Waikato Institute of Technology (WINTER) of New Zealand.

The NZSTIGS TTT program has the purpose of building the teaching skills and skills of trainers in the Indonesian geothermal industry and the education sector to ensure better learning outcomes. These programs will develop the skills of Instructors from MEMR and geothermal companies in Indonesia with pedagogical knowledge to provide ongoing support and effective training.

Exploration training PPSDM Geominerba

The Center for Human Resource Development of Geology, Minerals, and Coal (PPSDM Geominerba) is a merger of geology and mineral training centers in the framework of bureaucratic efficiency. This geological field covers all types of mining, including geothermal. This center has organized training on inventory, auction of geothermal, and exploration work areas in recent years.

Drilling training PPSDM Migas

The center of human resources development for oil and gas (PPSDM Migas) has been in operation for more than half a century under a different name. Currently, PPSDM employs approximately 280 employees, including 59 professional trainers and 70 laboratory staff.

The center offers various training programs which include long term apprentice programs, short courses, basic to advanced levels of training, and in-house training, even though it currently relies more on short-term training programs.

For drilling training, the center delivers around 30 training and drilling certification per year for floorman, derrickmen, drillers, and toolpushers. The training generally covers upstream oil and gas activities, well control techniques, BOP equipment, engineering and drill tools, and safety of drilling.

Figure 2. Number of trainees in PPSDM Migas since 2010 (PPSDM Migas, 2018)

PPSDM Migas is accredited by the International Association of Drilling Contractors (IADC) the USA and a member of the IWCF UK. The center is

also certified by the National Accreditation Committee (KAN), which is a member of the International Accreditation Forum (IAF).

In addition to regular drilling training for oil and gas and geothermal industries, the center has also undertaken training for a managerial level, which included drilling engineers and supervisors of Geothermal Well Drilling that was delivered in 2017. The training was a pilot course funded through the New Zealand Aid Programme by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade (MFAT) in cooperation with BPSDM. The aim of the training was to support Indonesia's geothermal sector by increasing the number of geothermal well drilling specialists as well as upgrading their competency.

The center also has its own professional certification body, namely LSP PPT Migas. The LSP began certifying from 1999 with accreditation from the National Accreditation Committee (KAN-BSP) and the National Personal Accreditation Committee (BNSP).

The scope of the certification in PPSDM Migas includes HSE, seismicity, drilling, production, and aviation. Most workers in the oil and gas industry in Indonesia indeed have been certified in PPSDM Migas. The certificate commonly has a valid period of three years and should be renewed by taking a new assessment.

The competency standards for drilling in Indonesia can be implemented for both geothermal, oil and gas industry (Umam et al., 2018). For drilling, certification is available for a floorman (level 2), a derrickman (level 3), a driller (level 4), and supervisor (level 5) which includes a toolpusher, rig superintendent, company man, and rig manager. The requirements for following (level 2-4) certification are a secondary education certificate and two years' experience at a lower level. To be able to take a driller certification, for example, a derrickman requires at least two years' experience as evidenced by a warrant from the company, while to earn a derrickman certification, two years' experience as a floorman is needed.

Figure 3. Certification takers at PPSDM Migas from 2012 to 2018 (PPSDM Migas, 2018)

This center, in collaboration with a geothermal company, had implemented Operation Maintenance Training with a duration of two and a half months last year. The training was attended by 23 students who were the prospective operators of geothermal power plants in Sumatra, all of which were local residents. This education and training program was a pilot project and is expected to be followed by further education and training with improvements on facilities and trainers.

EDUCATION BY STAKEHOLDERS

Universities

There are five universities currently have a geothermal department or research center as follows:

Institute of Technology Bandung (ITB)

ITB offers a four-semester master's program from 2008 under the Faculty of Mining and Petroleum Technology. The program covers a wide area of geothermal energy exploration, exploitation, utilization, management, economics, and environment.

The university also offers short courses to support the development of geothermal drilling in Indonesia. This course started as early as 1994 when ITB was in collaboration with the Geothermal Institute, University of Auckland to develop and deliver "Geothermal Technology, Teaching the Teachers" (Saptadji, 2010). Currently, there are 3-15 day short courses that are available for the public, which is divided into the engineering and geoscience group.

University of Gadjah Mada (UGM)

UGM, in collaboration with the University of Auckland and GNS Science, has been running geothermal basic and advanced courses since 2010. The five days courses are mainly for the staff of geothermal companies with a focus on geothermal engineering and geoscience.

University of Indonesia (UI)

The UI offers a Master in Geothermal Energy Exploration under the Department of Physics. Unfortunately, currently, there is no training in geothermal development by UI. With the availability of experts and trainers, however, the UI can be utilized for geothermal training in the future.

Institute of Technology Surabaya (ITS)

A Master Program of Geothermal Engineering in the ITS has been offered in the Department of Geomatics Engineering, under the Faculty of Civil, Environmental and Mechanical Engineering from 2009. The institute is located in East Java, which is the province with a potential of around 1300 MW, but currently has no utilization. Hence, it is expected

to help geothermal development in eastern Java Island.

University of Diponegoro (Undip)

The Undip has offered a Master of Energy program since 2014 although not specific in geothermal training. The university also has a center for geothermal research under the faculty of Science and Math. Like ITS, the university has an advantage because of its location in Central Java Province, which has about 1800 MW of geothermal potential, but only 60 MW is used (Dieng field). Thus, the university is expected to be utilized for future geothermal training.

Geothermal companies

Some geothermal operator companies have their training centers such as Pertamina and PLN. Within these training centers, prospective employees can be trained by the needs of the company. Unfortunately, since they are not for the public, these centers cannot be utilized for other companies.

International support

From its first commercial utilization, the geothermal industry in Indonesia has been assisted by international aid. The following is a summary of several international institutions that help Indonesia develop geothermal programs:

Netherlands (GEOCAP) geothermal capacity building program

The Geothermal Capacity Building Program Indonesia-Netherlands (GEOCAP) is an international collaboration between Indonesian and Dutch institutions to contribute a National Geothermal Capacity Building Programme (NGCBP). The goal of this program is to develop a close link between geothermal programs for education, training, and research such as universities, scientific institutions, and industrial partners. Further, this program also aims to support the Indonesian government to improve the utilization of geothermal resources by developing a database of subsurface layers.

Several organizations that involved in this program include the University of Twente, INAGA/API, TNO - Netherlands Organization for Applied Scientific Research, ITB, Delft Technical University (TUDelft), UI, UGM, Utrecht University, IF Technology, DNV-GL Energy, and Well Engineering Partners (WEP).

USAID

The Geothermal Education Capacity Building project funded by USAID was a university partnership between the University of Southern California (USC) and the ITB from 2012 to 2015. The program aimed to build the capacity of the geothermal education program at ITB with the

support of PT Star Energy, which is an Indonesian geothermal company.

USAID has also been working with the Indonesian Geothermal Association (INAGA) from 2011 to 2014 to deliver a geothermal Human Resource program that covers a master's degree course, training of trainers, and an introductory geothermal program. There was also technician-level training for staff of various geothermal producers including Pertamina Geothermal Energy (PGE), Supreme Energy, Star Energy, and Chevron Geothermal.

New Zealand Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade (MFAT)

MFAT regularly gives technical assistance and capacity building to accelerate Indonesia's geothermal development. The aim of the aid is mainly to support the Government of Indonesia's geothermal energy human resources development strategy. Beside NZSTIGS program, MFAT through GNS Science regularly delivers short courses in collaboration with UGM. Further, MFAT has organized some targeted training, which includes geothermal well drilling.

In the higher education level, about 60 post-graduate and 36 short-term training scholarships are offered to Indonesians to study in New Zealand. The majority of the awards are for renewable energy include geothermal followed by agriculture, disaster risk management, public sector leadership, and private sector development.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper is a review of competency needs in the geothermal industry, regulations related to the development of the geothermal human resource, capacity building programs by the MEMR, and support from stakeholders. It can be concluded that to meet geothermal human resource needs, both quality and quantity, all parties, both government, companies, and educational institutions, are needed. The government, through the Director General of EBTKE and the Human Resource Development Agency, has carried out various roles, including the preparation of SKKNI and training in the geothermal field.

However, many tasks must be done in the future, such as synergized policies with other stakeholders. This synergy problem can be seen as the mismatching between formal school graduates and the needs of the geothermal industry. Further, the capacity building program was sporadic, making the measurement of successfulness difficult.

Other stakeholders are also expected to be more proactive in developing geothermal human resources. In addition to increasing knowledge, it must be ensured that the skills acquired by competency development participants will be useful for the community. Beneficiaries are also expected to be more widespread so that the rejection of geothermal projects so far will decrease with the

massively spread of information about geothermal energy.

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